

Building and Setup Guide

Electromagnetic Gripper

Build

In making the gripper we begin from the electromagnet, for which it is necessary to start from a ferromagnetic core (a round with a diameter of 30 mm, 100 mm long), around which we make the winding.

For the winding a 27 AWG enamelled copper wire is used (minimum length 150 m) and it is necessary to make approximately 1550 turns of wire (which must correspond to a resistance value of 24 Ω) around the mentioned core, arranging them on several layers, making sure to maintain the same winding direction between one layer and another. To make winding easier, it is useful to use adhesive tape to fix the ends of the reel (especially when passing from one layer to another); in particular it is advisable to use kapton tape for its insulating properties and for its resistance to heat.

Once the winding has been completed and its resistance checked, the ends of the winding wire may be connected with two Dupont connectors to make the electromagnet connection modular; alternatively, these ends may be soldered directly to the wires that will carry the power supply.

Finally, we can proceed assembling the gripper shell, once printed, through four M2x15 screws and four M2 nuts, enclosing the electromagnet body within it and taking advantage of the hole provided at the base of the shell to pass the cables through.

Setup

Align the holes on the gripper shell with the four corresponding holes on the tool holder flange of the robot and secure the same with four M6x10 screws,

Tension (V)	Current (A)
24,0	1,0

Connect the two wires of the power supply to its outputs, respecting the polarities. Check the previous steps and the correct connection of all cables and, finally, activate the corresponding output of the power supply.

To activate or deactivate the gripper, it is necessary to act on the corresponding digital output.